

The Influence of Product Quality, Distribution Channels, and Promotion on Interest in Watching Acehese Music on Youtube

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Abstract:- This research was conducted to analyze the influence of product quality, distribution channels, and promotions on interest in watching Aceh YouTube music content. This quantitative study with a causal approach collected data from 68 respondents who actively watched Acehese music or songs. The data was analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with validity test, reliability test, R-Square test, F-Square test, interdimensional correlation analysis, and hypothesis testing. The results of this study state that product quality and promotion have a positive and significant effect, while distribution channels have no effect on interest in watching Acehese music on YouTube. This research suggests that Acehese music creators improve audio and visual quality and optimize advertisements to promote their works.

Keywords:- marketing mix, product quality, distribution channel, promotion, watching interest.

I. INTRODUCTION

The popularity of Acehese music, both at the local and national levels, is still low when compared to songs in other regional languages, for example songs in Malay, Minang, Javanese and Ambonese, although the audio and visual quality of Acehese songs can be said to be the same as songs in other regional languages. From random data collected by researchers, interest in watching music videos for Aceh songs is lower than songs in other regional languages, as shown in the following table:

Fig. 1: Average Number Views of Local Language Music Videos in Indonesia

Source: YouTube (2022)

The massive show of *Dangdut Koplo* on television has made this music consumed by audiences across geo-cultures [2]. Javanese-language songs are popular among young people and easily enter the national music market because Javanese-language songs are often shown and promoted on a number of television shows [3]. Television media has an important role in popularizing Javanese songs. An example is the “*Ambyar*” phenomenon, when Didi Kempot's *campursari* music colored almost all national television stations in the 2019-2020 period.

Previous studies have found that broadcast quality has a positive and significant effect on viewing interest [4]. Product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions [5]. Product quality is considered important by consumers and is used as the basis for consumer buying interest [6].

YouTube was built as a site or channel to distribute user generated content [7]. Distribution channels have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention and purchase decisions [8] [9], while other studies find advertising on YouTube has a positive effect on product purchase intention [10]. From these studies, it was found that aspects of product

quality, distribution channels, and promotions used to convey products or impressions to consumers, and promotional activities in the form of advertisements have an effect on viewing interest, purchase intention, or purchasing decisions. These aspects are elements in the marketing mix known as 4P.

To find out what marketing aspects influence interest in watching Aceh music videos on YouTube, researchers used four variables in this survey according to references from previous journals that have been described previously. The following are the results of the pre-survey obtained:

Fig. 2: Percentage of X1, X2, X3, and X4 pre-survey results

Based on Figure 2, the researcher takes data with a value above 50 percent (or close to 50 percent) to be included as a research variable. Variables that have values above 50% (or close to 50%) are Products, Channels, and Promotions which are then used as variables X1, variables X2, and variables X3.

Based on the formulation and theoretical studies that have been described, the research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

- H1: Product quality (X1) has an effect on interest in watching (Y).
- H2: Distribution channels (X2) have an effect on interest in watching (Y).
- H3: Promotion (X3) has an effect on interest in watching (Y).

Fig. 3: Framework

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The population in this study are journalists in Banda Aceh City who are members of journalist associations, namely the Alliance of Indonesian Journalists (AJI), the Association of Indonesian Journalists (PWI), the Indonesian Television Journalists Association (IJTI), and Indonesian Photojournalists (PFI). The taking of sample members from the population is done randomly without regard to the existing strata in the population. The requirements and sampling in this study are journalists who are members of the AJI, PWI, IJTI, and PFI associations who are stored in associations that are still active. From calculations using the

Slovin formula, the sample for this study was determined to be 68 people. Research data was obtained by distributing questionnaires using the Google Form application and then processed and analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Respondent Descriptions

This research involved a sample of 160 journalists from four professional organizations in Banda Aceh, Aceh, Indonesia. The descriptive analysis of the respondent's data explained by the following table:

Table 1: Respondent Characteristic

Respondent Characteristic		Amount	Percentage
Gender	Woman	12	18%
	Man	56	82%
Age	< 30 years old	21	31%
	30 – 40 years old	31	46%
	41 – 50 years old	14	21%
	> 50 years old	2	3%
Education	High school	9	13%
	Bachelor	53	78%
	Postgraduate	6	9%

B. Results of Data Analysis

➤ Outer Model

• Convergent Validity Test

Based on the data processing carried out, it was found that all loading factors were worth more than 0.70. So it can be concluded that based on each construct in the study has

good validity. To further strengthen the results of convergent validity, average variance extracted (AVE) testing was carried out with the criteria if the AVE value > 0.5 then the construct used in the study is valid [11]. The AVE results obtained are as follows:

Table 2: AVE Value

Latent	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	R critical	Criteria (AVE > 0.5)
Product Quality (X1)	0,572	0,5	Valid
Distribution Channel (X2)	0,666	0,5	Valid
Promotion (X3)	0,779	0,5	Valid
Interest in Watching (Y)	0,852	0,5	Valid

Based on table 2, it is known that the results of convergent validity are based on the AVE value. These results indicate that all latent variables have an AVE value of more than 0.5, which indicates that the indicators that form the latent construct have good convergent validity.

• Discriminant Validity Test

The discriminant validity test was carried out through Fornell-Lacker Criterion analysis, carried out by comparing the correlations between variables or constructs with the square root of AVE.

Table 3: Fornell Lacker Criterion

	X1.1	X1.2	X1.3	X1.4	X1.5	X1.6	X1.7	X2.1	X2.2	X2.3	Y1	Y2	Y3
X1.1	0.922												
X1.2	0.672	0.928											
X1.3	0.421	0.518	0.881										
X1.4	0.392	0.492	0.604	1.000									
X1.5	0.640	0.832	0.480	0.527	0.946								
X1.6	0.448	0.571	0.738	0.780	0.576	0.898							
X1.7	0.457	0.582	0.790	0.751	0.564	0.819	0.953						
X2.1	0.606	0.801	0.376	0.380	0.791	0.371	0.480	0.925					
X2.2	0.508	0.495	0.573	0.457	0.654	0.517	0.551	0.604	0.923				
X2.3	0.630	0.747	0.667	0.535	0.739	0.612	0.571	0.671	0.730	0.926			
Y1	0.396	0.460	0.549	0.519	0.380	0.676	0.521	0.336	0.410	0.606	1.000		
Y2	0.403	0.500	0.553	0.619	0.469	0.729	0.603	0.400	0.432	0.566	0.785	1.000	
Y3	0.236	0.289	0.575	0.539	0.269	0.729	0.619	0.160	0.343	0.404	0.780	0.768	1.000

Based on the results of discriminant validity testing using the Fornell-Lacker criterion, it can be seen that the AVE root (\sqrt{AVE}) for each construct is greater than the correlation between each construct and other constructs.

In addition, HTMT testing was carried out, namely the estimation of the actual correlation between the two constructs. Disattenuated Correlation between the two constructs close to 1 indicates a lack of discriminant validity.

Table 4: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	X1.1	X1.2	X1.3	X1.4	X1.5	X1.6	X1.7	X2.1	X2.2	X2.3	Y1	Y2	Y3
X1.1													
X1.2	0.809												
X1.3	0.553	0.670											
X1.4	0.430	0.537	0.707										
X1.5	0.748	0.863	0.603	0.558									
X1.6	0.565	0.705	0.888	0.892	0.695								
X1.7	0.531	0.668	0.884	0.791	0.631	0.887							
X2.1	0.729	0.860	0.492	0.417	0.825	0.464	0.556						
X2.2	0.613	0.591	0.739	0.502	0.764	0.653	0.639	0.728					
X2.3	0.762	0.888	0.865	0.586	0.860	0.767	0.659	0.805	0.879				
Y1	0.438	0.497	0.650	0.519	0.403	0.777	0.549	0.367	0.451	0.664			
Y2	0.445	0.542	0.655	0.619	0.498	0.837	0.635	0.437	0.476	0.620	0.785		
Y3	0.261	0.312	0.679	0.539	0.284	0.838	0.653	0.176	0.378	0.442	0.780	0.768	

There is no HTMT value above 0.90. This shows good discriminant validity.

• Reability Test

Table 5: Cronbach’s Alpha dan Composite Reliability

Latent	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Product Quality (X1)	0,937	0,945
Distribution Channel (X2)	0,900	0,923
Promotion (X3)	0,860	0,913
Interest in Watching (Y)	0,913	0,945

The test results found that the latent construct had Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values of more than 0.70. This shows that the model has good reliability.

➤ Outer Model

• R Square Test

Table 6: R Square

	R Square	Relations
Interest in Watching (Y)	0,532	Moderate

R Square with a value of 0.67 indicates a strong model, a value of 0.33 indicates a moderate model and a value of 0.19 indicates a weak model (Yamin and Kurniawan, 2011). From Table 6 it can be seen that the R-Square for the Interest in Watching (Y) variable is 0.532 which means that Product

Quality (X1), Distribution Channels (X2), and Promotion (X3) affect Interest in Watching (Y) by 53.2%. while the remaining 46.8% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

• f Square Test

Table 7: f Square

Variable	Effect Size	Rating
Interest in Watching (Y)		
Product Quality (X1)	0,144	Low
Distribution Channel (X2)	0,001	Low
Promotion (X3)	0,155	Moderate

To look at the value of f Square. An f Square value of 0.02 indicates a low rating, value of 0.15 indicates a medium

and value of 0.35 indicates a high rating (Yamin and Kurniawan, 2011).

- Q² Predictive Relevance

Table 8: Q² Predictive Relevance

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Product Quality (X1)	884.000	884.000	
Promosi (X3)	204.000	204.000	
Saluran Distribusi (X2)	408.000	408.000	
Minat Menonton (Y)	204.000	118.966	0.417

Based on the calculation results above, it is known that the Q square value is greater than 0, this means that the observed values have been reconstructed properly so that the model has predictive relevance.

➤ *Interdimensional Correlation Analysis*

- Effect of Product Quality (X1) on Interest in Watching (Y)
Data analysis obtained an original sample value (O) of 0.507. This shows that Product Quality (X1) has a positive and significant influence on Interest in Watching (Y).

- Effect of Distribution Channel (X2) on Interest in Watching (Y)
From the data analysis, the original sample value (O) was -0.045. This shows that Distribution Channels (X2) have no effect on Interest in Watching (Y).
- Effect of Promotion (X3) on Interest in Watching (Y)
From the data analysis, the original sample value (O) was obtained, which was 0.340. This shows that Promotion (X3) has a positive and significant influence on Interest in Watching (Y).

C. *Hypothesis Test Result*

The basis for decision making in hypothesis testing is if the P-Value < 0.05 then it has a significant effect and if the P-Value > 0.05 then it has no significant effect.

Table 9: Hypothesis Test Result

Effect	Original Sample (O)	t-Statistic	P-Value	Conclusion
Product Quality (X1) on Interest in Watching (Y)	0,507	2,073	0,039	H _{0.1} Rejected
Distribution Channel (X2) on Interest in Watching (Y)	-0,045	0,200	0,842	H _{0.2} Accepted
Promotion (X3) t on Interest in Watching (Y)	0,340	2,612	0,009	H _{0.3} Rejected

It is concluded as follows:

- H1: Product Quality (X1) has an effect on Interest in Watching (Y) is accepted.
- H2: Distribution Channel (X2) has an effect on Interest in Watching (Y) is rejected.
- H3: Promotion (X3) has an effect on Interest in Watching (Y) is accepted.

IV. CONCLUSION

Product Quality (X1) has an effect on Interest in Watching (Y). The most dominant dimension in describing product quality is the impression of good quality, and this has a significant effect on interest in watching Aceh music. Therefore, the better the quality of the uploaded videos and music, the greater the interest in watching them.

Distribution Channels (X2) have no effect on Interest in Watching (Y). The most dominant dimension in explaining distribution channels is related to availability, such as Aceh music content which is always available when desired and is in large and varied quantities. However, this availability does not affect viewing interest. This can happen because of the choice of various distribution channels, and not only on YouTube.

Promotion (X3) has an effect on Interest in Watching (Y). The most dominant dimension in explaining promotion is regarding music advertisements that look attractive, where this makes interest in watching Aceh music songs higher. Therefore, the more attractive the music ad displayed will have an impact on the higher interest in watching.

Thus, research on the Effects of Product Quality, Distribution Channels, and Promotion on Interest in Watching Aceh Music on Youtube has the following conclusions:

- Product Quality affects Interest in Watching.
- Distribution channels have no effect on Interest in Watching.
- Promotion has an effect on Interest in Watching.

V. REMARKS

- *Limitation:* Production Quality, Distribution Channels, and Promotions can only explain 53.2% of the influence on Interest in Watching, while the remaining 46.8% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. Subsequent research can add variables that have the potential to better explain Interest in Watching.

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